

Thioorthoester Polymers as Sulfur-Rich Materials in Metal Scavengers and Battery Cathodes

Jan Kraus⁺, Andreas Gruber⁺, Ruth Gomes, Dominic Iannitto, Kerstin Leopold,* and Max von Delius*

Editorial Summary: Sulfur-rich materials are key for semiconductors, metal binding, and battery electrodes. Inorganic sulfur cathodes are limited by capacity and cycling stability, and there is a need for alternative materials with high sulfur content. Leopold, von Delius, and co-workers applied dynamic covalent thioorthoester chemistry in an efficient synthesis of sulfur-rich networked polymers with high specific surface areas. The Scientific Advisory Committee of *Angewandte Chemie Novit* recognizes the emergence of a new group of sulfur-rich polymers as a remarkable advancement in precious-metal scavengers and battery materials.

Abstract: Polymeric materials with dynamic covalent carbon-heteroatom bonds are of significant interest for their stimuli-responsiveness and recyclability. This study investigates the utility of the dynamic covalent C–S bond in thioorthoesters for synthesizing networked polymers with a high sulfur content in the range of 44% to 66% by weight. The synthesis utilizes economical and abundant reagents through polycondensation, resulting in networked polymer materials insoluble in all tested solvents. The combination of high sulfur content and porous surface structure ensures excellent sorption characteristics beneficial for scavenging precious metals such as palladium and toxic metalloids such as antimony. Additionally, the thioorthoester polymers show potential as cathodes in rechargeable lithium ion batteries, suggesting diverse applications for these sulfur-rich materials.

The sulfur atom^[1] occupies a special place in the toolbox of organic materials chemistry. The fact that so many organic semiconductors for instance contain thiophenes^[2,3] is thanks to sulfur, which endows this particular heteroarene with desirable properties such as high chemical stability, convenient functionalization chemistry, and favorable frontier orbital energies.^[4] Sulfur atoms are also utilized as “soft” ligands for the binding of precious metals in commercial scavenger materials,^[5–7] such as QuadraPure TU (thiourea on resin)^[8] or SiliaMetS DMT (dimercaptotriazine on silica).^[9] Recently, the rich redox chemistry of elemental sulfur has been utilized in the cathode of lithium–sulfur batteries^[10–12] that offer extremely high theoretical capacity (1672 mAh g^{−1}).^[10,13–15] To minimize or completely avoid the leakage of small

“oligosulfide” fragments into the electrolyte of Li–S batteries, a substantial body of work has recently been devoted to “inverse vulcanization” materials that contain sulfur chains of limited length^[16–20] and to materials containing immobilized disulfide bonds (Figure 1).^[21–23]

Over the past decade, our group has explored orthoester exchange^[24] as a previously ignored dynamic covalent reaction^[25–27] that allows the synthesis of adaptive supramolecular hosts^[28–32] and degradable polymer materials.^[33] In a preliminary study with the group of Furlan, who are experts in thioacetal exchange,^[34–40] we investigated the chemistry of *S,S,S*-thioorthoesters as the sulfur analogues of *O,O,O*-orthoesters (Figure 1a).^[41] While thioorthoester exchange has been studied and used in the context of organic multi-step synthesis,^[42] most notably by Seebach,^[43,44] we were

[*] J. Kraus⁺, Dr. R. Gomes, Prof. Dr. M. von Delius
Institute of Organic Chemistry, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm, Germany
E-mail: max.vondelius@uni-ulm.de

A. Gruber⁺, D. Iannitto, Prof. Dr. K. Leopold
Institute of Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm, Germany
E-mail: kerstin.leopold@uni-ulm.de

[⁺] Both authors contributed equally to this work.

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section

© 2025 The Author(s). Angewandte Chemie Novit published by Wiley-VCH GmbH on behalf of Gesellschaft Deutscher Chemiker (GDCh; the German Chemical Society). This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Figure 1. a) Thioorthoester exchange. b) Networked thioorthoester polymers.

Figure 2. a) Synthesis of networked polymer materials **3a–c** by thioorthoester exchange. Reaction conditions: **1** (1 equiv.), **2a**, **2b**, or **2c** (1.5 equiv.), FeCl_3 (10 mol%); given values in parentheses correspond to product yields (as recovered mass yield, see Supplementary Information). b) Photographs of **3a–c** (top) together with SEM images (bottom). c) TGA of **3a–c** (10 K min^{-1} , N_2 atmosphere). d) FT-IR spectra of polymers **3a–c** (**3a** top, **3b** center, **3c** bottom). e) ^{13}C CP-/HPDEC-MAS NMR (15 kHz rotation, 101 MHz) spectra of **3a–c** (**3a** and **3b**: ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR, **3c**: ^{13}C HPDEC-MAS NMR; **3a** top, **3b** center, **3c** bottom).

surprised when we identified relatively mild conditions (e.g., 10% FeCl_3) for the exchange reaction,^[41] which made us wonder why networked thioorthoester polymer materials are extremely rare^[45,46] despite their obvious appeal for the applications described above.

Herein, we show how the condensation reaction between a commercially available thioorthoester (**1**) with simple dithiols (**2**) can be used to prepare networked polymer materials that are intrinsically rich in sulfur (Figure 1b). We report preliminary experiments demonstrating the utility of these thioorthoester materials as highly effective scavengers for precious metals (e.g., Pd, Ag, Au, Pt) and as organic cathodes in rechargeable lithium batteries.

To prepare the envisaged, networked thioorthoester polymers, we treated commercially available tris(methylthio)methane (**1**) with flexible dithiols (**2a–c**, Figure 2a) under conditions suitable for thioorthoester exchange.

The optimized reaction conditions featured anhydrous benzonitrile as solvent, 10 mol% iron(III) chloride as catalyst, and a temperature of $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. To shift the equilibrium in these condensation reactions toward the polymeric products, the byproduct MeSH was continuously removed by placing the reaction mixture under a stream of argon gas (see Scheme S2 for the proposed reaction mechanism). In case of starting materials **2a** and **2b**, colorless, rubbery solids were obtained (**3a–b**, Figure 2b). The disulfide-containing starting material **2c** led to product **3c**, which was obtained as a powder. All three polymer materials were insoluble in water and organic solvents. Upon treatment with water, the fluffy rubber-like solids began to shrink in size, whereas tetrahydrofuran (THF) led to swelling.

The optimized synthesis conditions shown in Figure 2 were identified by variation of all relevant reaction parameters. We found that heating of the reaction mixture was

beneficial for obtaining solid polymer material in high yields. Tris(methylthio)methane (**1**) and dithiols **2a–c** were used in a stoichiometric ratio of 1 and 1.5 equiv., respectively, due to the number of functionalities (3 for thioorthoester **1**, 2 for dithiols **2a–c**). Benzonitrile is the preferred solvent, as it is non-toxic and more environmentally benign than other effective solvents such as chloroform or acetonitrile. The higher boiling point of benzonitrile also prevents the reaction vessels from running dry despite being placed under a stream of argon at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Further details about the parameter optimization, most notably a survey of Brønsted and Lewis acid catalysts, can be found in Table S1.^[41]

Photographs of the polymer materials demonstrate their colorless, solid appearance (Figure 2b); scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images reveal porous microscale morphologies that seem ideally suited for applications that require large surface areas (Figures 2b, S24–S26). Further characterization was achieved by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR), and cross-polarization magic angle spinning (CP-MAS) ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. TGA curves show only small differences between the three materials (Figure 2c) with the ether-linked polymer **3b** exhibiting thermal degradation at the highest temperature (ca. $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). FT-IR spectra of **3a** and **3c** (Figures 2d, S20) show characteristic peaks for C–S bonds ($1410\text{--}1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, purple and $740\text{--}680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, green); **3b** shows an additional highly intense peak indicative of C–O bonds ($1100\text{--}1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, yellow colored). Material **3c** was also studied by Raman spectroscopy (Figure S23), revealing peaks at 506 and 726 cm^{-1} that correlate with the presence of IR-inactive disulfide bonds (in agreement with literature known disulfide compounds).^[47,48] All ^{13}C MAS spectra (Figure 2e) show signals at ca. 57 ppm (orthoester carbon atoms, red colored) and ca. 33 ppm (carbon atoms appended

Figure 3. a) Schematic overview of the performed metal adsorption experiments. Addition of polymer material **3a** to aqueous solutions of metal nitrates (Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II), Ag(I), Cd(II), Tl(I), Pb(II), Bi(III)), metal chlorides (Sn(IV), Sb(III), Pt(IV), Au(III)), and As₂O₃, respectively, (element concentration ca. 1 mg L⁻¹; pH 2.5–5 after addition of element solutions) was followed by shaking of the mixture at r.t. for 1 h and determination of the metal content by quantitative element analysis. b) Section of the periodic table summarizing the mass-weighted coefficients ($q_{60 \text{ min}}$) for analytes sorbed by polymer **3a** in aqueous solution after 60 min. Elements Zn, Hg, Ga, In, Ge were not selected for the test for practical reasons.

to the thioether, blue colored). For materials **3b** and **3c**, characteristic signals for the ether (in **3b**, yellow colored) and disulfide (in **3c**, green colored) functionalities are observed. Elemental analysis (EA) data (Supplementary Information) further corroborate the chemical structure and purity of materials **3a–c**.

Following their characterization, we explored two applications of these inherently networked and sulfur-rich materials. In adsorption experiments, we tested whether the (thio)ether-linked materials **3a** and **3b** can be used as metal scavengers. First, the new materials were tested in aqueous solution, as innovative adsorbents are essential for the effective removal of heavy metals from waters.^[49,50] Because initial studies pointed toward better performance of the thioether material **3a**, we investigated this specific material for adsorption of selected metals belonging to the group of technology-critical and (eco)toxic elements.^[51] Figure 3a shows schematically how these isotherm sorption experiments were carried out. Portions of polymer material **3a** (ca. 30 mg) were added to dilute (ca. 1 mg L⁻¹) aqueous solutions of metal salts, and the mixtures were shaken for 1 h at room temperature. Samples

were taken from the liquid supernatant and subjected to quantitative element analysis using either total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (TXRF) or graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GFAAS) to determine the metal content. The analysis was carried out in triplicate, and control experiments without added polymer material were performed to rule out non-specific adsorption and contamination issues.

The results of these sorption experiments are summarized graphically in Figure 3b. The sorption efficiency of polymer **3a** increases in the order Sb < Cu < Pt < Bi < Ag < Au < Pd under the conditions of the experiment. Elements shown in light yellow were also tested but showed no adsorption, indicating a remarkable specificity for certain coinage metals (Pd: 0.84 mg g⁻¹, Au: 0.75 mg g⁻¹, Ag: 0.55 mg g⁻¹) over heavy metals such as Cd or Pb (both 0 mg g⁻¹) that would typically be expected to bind to thioethers.^[52] We can currently only speculate that the size of the pores as well as the specific coordination geometry within the pores is causing the observed selectivity in water.

To explore potential applications, we chose two exemplary elements, Sb and Pd, to study sorption in more detail. Sb is a carcinogenic pollutant that needs to be removed during wastewater treatment.^[53] Very few commercial scavengers are available for this element. The sorption capacity of polymer **3a** for Sb using the Langmuir pseudo-second-order (PSO) isotherm adsorption model^[54,55] reaches a maximum equilibrium sorption capacity (q_e) of $2.23 \pm 0.12 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ (Table S3, Figure S28a). Although this may not seem very high compared to, e.g., an estimated value of $\leq 25 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ for the commercial scavenger “SiliaMetS AMPA” from SiliCycle (Equation 2 in Supporting Information), the polymer shows significant reusability with a desorption efficiency of up to 83% at room temperature and a capacity reduction of only 23% upon reuse. These properties are superior to commercial scavengers and most materials described in the literature,^[53] which often show no reusability or significantly poorer capacity retention.

The sorption capacity of palladium was studied using the same PSO model (Figure S28c), because the removal of Pd from pharmaceutical products is one of the most important applications of scavenger materials.^[5–7,56] Under technologically relevant conditions,^[8] i.e.,^[54,55] Pd(OAc)₂ salt (ca. 0.4 mM) in the organic solvent THF,^[8] we observed a highly encouraging maximum equilibrium sorption capacity ($q_e = 41.2 \pm 0.4 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) on polymer **3a** (ca. 16 mg) which even outcompetes the sorption capacity that we determined for the commercial scavenger material QuadraPure TU ($q_e = 22.2 \pm 1.0 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) under identical conditions.

Owing to the presence of redox-active disulfide bonds in polymer material **3c**, we explored its potential as a cathode material in rechargeable lithium batteries. To obtain a conductive hybrid material, we synthesized polymer **3c** in the presence of single-walled carbon nanotubes (**3c/SWCNT**, 20.5 wt% SWCNT as determined by TGA, Figure S18, green curve). Figures S21 and S27 show the FT-IR spectra and SEM images, respectively, of the composite material **3c/SWCNT**. To investigate the performance of the polymer composite **3c/SWCNT**, electrodes comprising a 7:2:1 weight

Figure 4. Battery performance of the hybrid polymer material **3c/SWCNT** (mixed with 20 wt% carbon black and 10 wt% PVDF binder) as cathode against Li. a) Cycling performance at current rate 0.5 C; b) Constant current charge–discharge profile for selected cycles; c) Schematic representation of the redox processes during battery charging and discharging.

ratio of active material (**3c/SWCNT**), conducting carbon black, and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) binder were assembled in a half-cell configuration against lithium, utilizing 1 M LiTFSI + 0.25 M LiNO₃ dissolved in a 1:1 (v:v) mixture of dioxolane (DOL) and dimethoxyethane (DME) as the electrolyte. The cyclic voltammogram (Figure S29) exhibited a broad reduction peak in the region 1.85–1.45 V (reduction of the disulfide), accompanied by a broad oxidation peak ranging between 2.4 and 2.8 V (reversible oxidation of lithium sulfides).

Subsequently, we recorded the galvanostatic charge–discharge cycling performance of the material at a current rate of 0.5 C over 1000 cycles (Figure 4a). The material demonstrated an initial specific discharge capacity of 188 mAh g⁻¹, which experienced a notable decline during the earlier cycles (133 mAh g⁻¹ @25th cycle). However, following this initial decline, the material exhibited a nearly stable cycling behavior for 1000 cycles, with minimal capacity fading (93 mAh g⁻¹ @1000 cycles) and a Coulombic efficiency of roughly 100%. Thus, the reversible redox activity of the polymer was consistently maintained over an extensive number of cycles. The galvanostatic charge–discharge profiles for selected cycles depicted in Figure 4b exhibit a resemblance to the reversible redox behavior observed in the cyclic voltammogram. Overall, the observed specific capacity is in a similar range as that reported for related battery cathodes^[57–59]; the stability over a large number of cycles

confirmed our hypothesis that disulfide-linked thioorthoester cathodes do not suffer from the problem of dissolution of cathode fragments into the electrolyte.

In conclusion, we report a straightforward and economically viable synthesis of networked thioorthoester polymer materials that are inherently sulfur-rich. Preliminary data on the use of these materials as metal scavengers and battery cathodes are highly promising. Our approach has a crucial advantage over “inverse vulcanization” methods^[16–20] that incorporate elemental sulfur: thioorthoester material **3c** incorporates discrete disulfide bonds rather than oligosulfide chains, preventing leakage of oligosulfides into the electrolyte. Future work will focus on high-value scavenger applications (Pd: removal from pharmaceuticals; Sb: removal from wastewater; Au: extraction from seawater), improved battery performance, and harnessing the unique advantages of dynamic covalent polymers (depolymerization, healing, and recycling).

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge financial support by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) under project numbers DE-1830/5-1 (M.v.D.), 390874152 “POLiS” Cluster of Excellence (M.v.D., K.L.), 445471845, 445471097, and 445470598. M.v.D. thanks the European Research Council (ERC, grant no. 802428, SUPRANET). The authors also thank Dr. G. Neusser and the Focused Ion Beam Center (Ulm University) for SEM measurements, Dr. R. Witter (HIU), and C. Tontsch (Ulm University) for recording MAS NMR spectra, B. Beitzinger (Ulm University) for Raman measurements, and S. Özkan for assistance with synthesis.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

Keywords: Battery cathodes • Dynamic covalent chemistry • Networked polymers • Organosulfur polymers • Scavenger materials

- [1] S. Matile, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2019**, *25*, 6460.
- [2] *Handbook of Thiophene-Based Materials: Applications in Organic Electronics and Photonics* (Eds.: I. F. Perepichka, D. F. Perepichka), John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Chichester **2009**.
- [3] G. Turkoglu, M. E. Cinar, T. Ozturk, *Top. Curr. Chem.* **2017**, *375*, 84.
- [4] A. Mishra, P. Bäuerle, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 2020–2067.

- [5] N. Galaffu, S. P. Man, R. D. Wilkes, J. R. H. Wilson, *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2007**, *11*, 406–413.
- [6] M. Economidou, N. Mistry, K. M. P. Wheelhouse, D. M. Lindsay, *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2023**, *27*, 1585–1615.
- [7] H. Miyamoto, C. Sakumoto, E. Takekoshi, Y. Maeda, N. Hiramoto, T. Itoh, Y. Kato, *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2015**, *19*, 1054–1061.
- [8] A. Hinchcliffe, C. Hughes, D. A. Pears, M. R. Pitts, *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2007**, *11*, 477–481.
- [9] V. W. Rosso, D. A. Lust, P. J. Bernot, J. A. Grosso, S. P. Modi, A. Rusowicz, T. C. Sedergran, J. H. Simpson, S. K. Srivastava, M. J. Humora, N. G. Anderson, *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **1997**, *1*, 311–314.
- [10] A. Manthiram, Y. Fu, S.-H. Chung, C. Zu, Y.-S. Su, *Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *114*, 11751–11787.
- [11] A. Manthiram, S.-H. Chung, C. Zu, *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 1980–2006.
- [12] R. Fang, S. Zhao, Z. Sun, D.-W. Wang, H.-M. Cheng, F. Li, *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, *29*, 1606823.
- [13] Q. Pang, X. Liang, C. Y. Kwok, L. F. Nazar, *Nat. Energy* **2016**, *1*, 16132.
- [14] P. G. Bruce, S. A. Freunberger, L. J. Hardwick, J.-M. Tarascon, *Nat. Mater.* **2012**, *11*, 19–29.
- [15] R. Fang, J. Xu, D.-W. Wang, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2020**, *13*, 432–471.
- [16] W. J. Chung, J. J. Griebel, E. T. Kim, H. Yoon, A. G. Simmonds, H. J. Ji, P. T. Dirlam, R. S. Glass, J. J. Wie, N. A. Nguyen, B. W. Guralnick, J. Park, Á. Somogyi, P. Theato, M. E. Mackay, Y.-E. Sung, K. Char, J. Pyun, *Nat. Chem.* **2013**, *5*, 518–524.
- [17] P. T. Dirlam, R. S. Glass, K. Char, J. Pyun, *J. Polym. Sci. Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2017**, *55*, 1635–1668.
- [18] H. Mutlu, E. B. Ceper, X. Li, J. Yang, W. Dong, M. M. Ozmen, P. Theato, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2019**, *40*, 1800650.
- [19] A. Hoeffling, D. T. Nguyen, P. Partovi-Azar, D. Sebastiani, P. Theato, S.-W. Song, Y. J. Lee, *Chem. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 2915–2923.
- [20] T. Lee, P. T. Dirlam, J. T. Njardarson, R. S. Glass, J. Pyun, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2022**, *144*, 5–22.
- [21] P. Sang, Q. Chen, D.-Y. Wang, W. Guo, Y. Fu, *Chem. Rev.* **2023**, *123*, 1262–1326.
- [22] J. Bitenc, K. Pirnat, O. Lužanin, R. Dominko, *Chem. Mater.* **2024**, *36*, 1025–1040.
- [23] Z. Shadike, S. Tan, Q.-C. Wang, R. Lin, E. Hu, D. Qu, X.-Q. Yang, *Mater. Horiz.* **2021**, *8*, 471–500.
- [24] R.-C. Brachvogel, M. von Delius, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, *6*, 1399–1403.
- [25] P. T. Corbett, J. Leclaire, L. Vial, K. R. West, J.-L. Wietor, J. K. M. Sanders, S. Otto, *Chem. Rev.* **2006**, *106*, 3652–3711.
- [26] F. B. L. Coughon, A. R. Stefankiewicz, S. Ulrich, *Chem. Sci.* **2024**, *15*, 879–895.
- [27] *Dynamic Covalent Chemistry: Principles, Reactions and Applications* (Eds.: W. Zhang, Y. Jin), John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Chichester **2017**.
- [28] S. Hollstein, M. von Delius, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2024**, *57*, 602–612.
- [29] R.-C. Brachvogel, F. Hampel, M. von Delius, *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 7129.
- [30] X. Wang, O. Shyshov, M. Hanževački, C. M. Jäger, M. von Delius, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 8868–8876.
- [31] S. Hollstein, O. Shyshov, M. Hanževački, J. Zhao, T. Rudolf, C. M. Jäger, M. von Delius, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, *61*, e202201831.
- [32] S. Hollstein, P. Erdmann, A. Ulmer, H. Löw, L. Greb, M. von Delius, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, e202304083.
- [33] T. Haider, O. Shyshov, O. Suraeva, I. Lieberwirth, M. von Delius, F. R. Wurm, *Macromolecules* **2019**, *52*, 2411–2420.
- [34] A. G. Orrillo, R. L. E. Furlan, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, *61*, e202201168.
- [35] A. G. Orrillo, A. M. Escalante, R. L. E. Furlan, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2016**, *22*, 6746–6749.
- [36] A. G. Orrillo, A. La-Venia, A. M. Escalante, R. L. E. Furlan, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2018**, *24*, 3141–3146.
- [37] A. G. Orrillo, A. M. Escalante, R. L. E. Furlan, *Org. Lett.* **2017**, *19*, 1446–1449.
- [38] M. Martinez-Amezaga, A. G. Orrillo, R. L. E. Furlan, *Chem. Sci.* **2019**, *10*, 8338–8347.
- [39] L. S. Kariyawasam, J. F. Highmoore, Y. Yang, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, e202303039.
- [40] S. Du, S. Yang, B. Wang, P. Li, J. Zhu, S. Ma, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2024**, *63*, e202405653.
- [41] M. Bothe, A. G. Orrillo, R. L. E. Furlan, M. von Delius, *Synlett* **2019**, *30*, 1988–1994.
- [42] B. Mao, K. Geurts, M. Fañanás-Mastral, A. W. van Zijl, S. P. Fletcher, A. J. Minnaard, B. L. Feringa, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 948–951.
- [43] D. Seebach, K.-H. Geiß, A. K. Beck, B. Graf, H. Daum, *Chem. Ber.* **1972**, *105*, 3280–3300.
- [44] B. T. Gröbel, D. Seebach, *Synthesis* **1977**, *1977*, 357–402.
- [45] R. Cameron, J. Zook, *Low Viscosity Polythiol and Method Therefor*, US5225472A **1993**, <https://patents.google.com/patent/US5225472A/en>.
- [46] F. Muehito, T. Mamoru, K. Shigenori, K. Seiichi, *Polythiol, Method of Production for the Same, Polymer Composition Containing The Same, and Resin and Lenz*, JP2003212843A, **2003**, <https://worldwide.espacenet.com/patent/search/family/027644746/publication/JP2003212843A?q=pn%3DJP2003212843A>.
- [47] B. Hernández, F. Pflüger, E. López-Tobar, S. G. Kruglik, J. V. Garcia-Ramos, S. Sanchez-Cortes, M. Ghomi, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* **2014**, *45*, 657–664.
- [48] P. Bazylewski, R. Divigalpitaya, G. Fanchini, *RSC Adv.* **2017**, *7*, 2964–2970.
- [49] M. Bilal, I. Ihsanullah, M. Younas, M. Ul Hassan Shah, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **2021**, *278*, 119510.
- [50] S. Rajendran, A. K. Priya, P. Senthil Kumar, T. K. A. Hoang, K. Sekar, K. Y. Chong, K. S. Khoo, H. S. Ng, P. L. Show, *Chemosphere* **2022**, *303*, 135146.
- [51] D. H. Dang, M. Filella, D. Omanović, *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* **2021**, *81*, 517–520.
- [52] S. M. Williams, J. S. Brodbelt, A. P. Marchand, D. Cal, K. Mlinaric-Majerski, *Anal. Chem.* **2002**, *74*, 4423–4433.
- [53] M. A. Carneiro, A. M. A. Pintor, R. A. R. Boaventura, C. M. S. Botelho, *Sci. Total Environ.* **2024**, *929*, 172602.
- [54] J.-P. Simonin, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2016**, *300*, 254–263.
- [55] J. Wang, X. Guo, *Chemosphere* **2020**, *258*, 127279.
- [56] J. Rayadurgam, S. Sana, M. Sasikumar, Q. Gu, *Org. Chem. Front.* **2021**, *8*, 384–414.
- [57] Q. Fan, Y. Si, W. Guo, Y. Fu, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2021**, *12*, 900–906.
- [58] T. Shimizu, H. Wang, D. Matsumura, K. Mitsuhara, T. Ohta, H. Yoshikawa, *ChemSusChem* **2020**, *13*, 2256–2263.
- [59] D.-Y. Wang, W. Guo, Y. Fu, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2019**, *52*, 2290–2300.

Manuscript received: April 14, 2025

Revised manuscript received: April 29, 2025

Version of record online: ■ ■ ■ ■ ■

Communication

J. Kraus, A. Gruber, R. Gomes, D. Iannitto,
K. Leopold*, M. von Delius* — e70000

Thioorthoester Polymers as Sulfur-Rich
Materials in Metal Scavengers and Battery
Cathodes

A facile method for the preparation of bulk quantities of networked thioorthoester polymers is reported. The produced materials combine exceptionally high sulfur content with surface porosity and therefore exhibit excellent performance as scavengers for precious metals such as Pd and promising characteristics as organic battery cathodes.

